

Н. В. Чехов: педагог и организатор народного образования

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. Действительный член Академии педагогических наук (далее – АПН) РСФСР Николай Владимирович Чехов (1865-1947) вошел в историю отечественного образования как видный педагог последней четверти XIX – первой половины XX вв. Вся его жизнь представляет пример беззаветного служения интересам российского народа.

Материалы и методы. Автором применялись следующие научно-исследовательские методы: исторический и биографический, анализ научно-педагогической, мемуарной и краеведческой литературы, а также аксиологический и региональный подходы, что позволило выделить все самое ценное в педагогическом наследии Чехова и выявить мнения о нем со стороны его современников и учеников. В процессе работы использовались публикации ряда российских и зарубежных исследователей.

Результаты. В студенческие годы Чехов состоял в студенческом научном обществе, секретарем которого был А. И. Ульянов. В дальнейшем Чехов на протяжении более 60 лет трудился в качестве рядового учителя и заведующего школой, администратора районного (уездного) масштаба, причем первую половину своей многолетней деятельности он трудился в условиях царского самодержавия, а вторую – при советской власти. При этом ему неизменно удавалось оставаться самим собой, не изменять принципам гуманизма и социальной справедливости. Чехов был одним из соучредителей Академии педагогических наук РСФСР (1943), автором значительного числа ценных пособий и книг. Всего им опубликовано примерно 800 материалов.

Обсуждение. Н. В. Чехову приходилось вступать в научные споры с другими специалистами, в частности, отстаивать правомерность самого понятия «детская литература». Он выступал против «серых» книг, «пинкертощины», «ходульности» и других недостатков. Он выступал за создание нового типа учителя, сочетавшего в себе глубокие знания и любовь к родному народу.

Заключение. Чехов был одним из тех деятелей народного образования, кто прокладывал пути развития отечественной системы образования и педагогической науки. Высокую оценку его многогранной деятельности давали народный комиссар просвещения В. П. Потемкин, аспирант из г. Вятка, передовой педагог А. И. Кондаков и другие современники. Теоретическое наследие Чехова заслуживает дальнейшего изучения.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

Чехов, Миллер, Ульянов, Ольминский, земская школа, воскресная школы, съезды деятелей по техническому и профессиональному образованию, Кондаков, Тихомиров, Потемкин

Для цитирования: Помелов В. Б. Н. В. Чехов: педагог и организатор народного образования // Перспективы науки и образования. 2025. № 4. С. 450–459. <https://doi.org/10.32744/pse.2025.4.29>

Поступила: 22.02.2024 | Одобрена: 13.04.2025 | Опубликована: 31.08.2025

Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

N. V. Chekhov: teacher and organizer of public education

V. B. POMELOV

ABSTRACT

Introduction. Nikolai Vladimirovich Chekhov (1865-1947), a full member of the Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of the RSFSR (further – APS), entered the history of Russian education as a prominent teacher of the last quarter of the XIX – first half of the XX centuries. His whole life is an example of selfless service to the interests of the Russian people.

Materials and methods. The author used the following research methods: historical and biographical, analysis of scientific and pedagogical, memoir and local history literature, as well as axiological and regional approaches, which made it possible to highlight all the most valuable things in Chekhov's pedagogical heritage and identify opinions about him from his contemporaries and students. The publications of a number of Russian and foreign researchers were used in the process of work.

Results. During his student years, Chekhov was a member of the student scientific society, whose secretary was A. I. Ulyanov. Later, Chekhov worked for more than 60 years as an ordinary teacher and head of a school, an administrator of a district (county) scale, and for the first half of his many years of activity he worked under the conditions of the tsarist autocracy, and the second half under Soviet rule. At the same time, he always managed to remain himself, not to change the principles of humanism and social justice. Chekhov was one of the co-founders of the APS (1943), the author of a significant number of valuable manuals and books. In total, he has published about 800 materials.

Discussion. Chekhov had to enter into scientific disputes with other specialists, in particular, to defend the legitimacy of the very concept of "children's literature". He opposed "gray" books, "pinkertonism", "stiltedness" and other shortcomings. He advocated the creation of a new type of teacher who combined deep knowledge and love for his native people.

Conclusion. Chekhov was one of those figures of public education who paved the way for the development of the national education system and pedagogical science. People's Commissar of Education V. P. Potemkin, a graduate student from Vyatka, an advanced teacher A. I. Kondakov and other contemporaries highly appreciated his multifaceted activities. Chekhov's theoretical legacy deserves further study.

KEYWORDS

Chekhov, Miller, Ulyanov, Olminsky, zemstvo school, Sunday schools, congresses of figures on technical and vocational education, Kondakov, Tikhomirov, Potemkin

For Citation: Pomelov, V. B. (2025). N. V. Chekhov: teacher and organizer of public education. *Perspektivy nauki i obrazovania = Perspectives of Science and Education*, (4), 450–459. <https://doi.org/10.32744/pse.2025.4.29>

Received: 22 February 2025 | Approved: 13 April 2025 | Published: 31 August 2025

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INTRODUCTION

On October 5, 1966, a special intergovernmental conference convened by UNESCO and the International Labour Organization (ILO) adopted the so-called "Recommendation on the Status of Teachers" [1]. This international document was designed to protect the position of the teaching profession, to define professional standards in the field of education and working conditions of teachers. It confirms the right of every citizen to receive education, which is recorded in the Declaration of Human Rights [2]. The recommendation includes 146 articles, which are grouped into the following thematic sections: teacher training and advanced training, employment, promotion, job security, disciplinary measures, part-time work, professional freedoms, monitoring and evaluation of work, duties and rights, participation in decision-making on educational issues, dialogue with the employer, conditions for an effective learning process, social security. Despite the fact that more than fifty years have passed since the adoption of the Recommendation, the importance and relevance of this international document, adopted by the legislative bodies of more than a hundred states, remain fully relevant to the present day, since ideas, principles and approaches embedded in it continue to have a direct impact on formation and improvement of legislation on education in different countries of the world [3, p. 37]. In this regard, UNESCO declared Teacher's Day an international holiday in 1994, which is celebrated worldwide on October 5.

Since the adoption of the Recommendation, statesmen around the world have begun to consider it as a set of guidelines aimed at improving the situation of teachers in the interests of ensuring the quality of education and, if possible, reaching the entire population. Another UNESCO Recommendation, "On the status of teaching staff in higher education institutions", was adopted by the UNESCO General Conference in 1997 after many years of preparatory work carried out by this organization and the ILO. This legal standard is a set of recommendations covering university teaching staff. It was developed in addition to the 1966 Recommendation, and UNESCO and the ILO are engaged in its popularization and monitoring of its application. As UNESCO Director-General Koichiro Matsuura and ILO Director-General Juan Somavia note in their joint statement, work continues together with UN member states and public partners to monitor and promote compliance with the principles laid down in these two normative acts, which are essential for the implementation of a sound policy towards teachers [4].

Teachers of secondary and higher education are constantly searching for the best solutions in their desire to achieve the highest learning outcomes [5]. Their use of truly new learning tools, including in the field of visualization, attracts attention [6]. Teachers use integrating visual thinking strategies as didactic tools [7]. Visual aids also remain in the arsenal of advanced educators [8]. As before, in publications of foreign researchers, a significant place is occupied by the issues of use of traditional means due to the personal characteristics of the teacher [9]. These include, in particular, emotions and love for children [10]. Great importance is attached to the study of humanistic education: concerns, implications, and applications [11]. The correlation of teacher / student control ideology and burnout attracts the attention of researchers [12]. Researchers are also studying the teacher's mindset [13]. There is no doubt that success in education is based on the activity of a teacher who is able to solve the most difficult problems in the process of carrying out his work [14]. The analysis of fruitful activity of teachers makes up a significant part of pedagogical publications [15]. The work of progressive educators is based on a humanistic approach [16], as well as the humanistic interaction of all participants in pedagogical process [17]. An interesting form of humanistic interaction can be the so-called learning communities [18].

In the history of Russian education, the tradition of humanism has deep roots and is traditionally considered one of the integral parts of Russian pedagogical thinking. N. V. Chekhov is one of the largest Russian humanist teachers. At one time, he was considered one of the most significant Russian figures of public education, both in the pre-October period and during the years of Soviet power. His multifaceted, tireless work in the field of education has earned him great popularity and love in the widest teaching circles. It was a rare case for famous teachers of his generation, – after October 1917 he didn't get lost in an unusual social environment, didn't engage in frontage towards the new government, but continued, as before, to work hard and successfully cooperated with the Soviet government until the end of his life, for exactly 30 more years! His services to national education and pedagogical science are very significant, but there are very few biographical articles

about him; after his death, his works weren't published at all. Therefore, his name and glorious deeds in the field of education and pedagogy began to be gradually forgotten. We considered it necessary to remind modern teachers about this remarkable man, and for this purpose we have compiled a fairly complete account of his biography and main works.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the course of his work, the author used biographical and historical research methods, the method of working with scientific literature, as well as an axiological approach to analyzing the pedagogical heritage of a prominent Russian teacher, which made it possible to identify the most valuable in the scientific works and practical educational activities of N. V. Chekhov. The author also used a regional approach, which made it possible to identify his connections with representatives of education from the Russian province. In the process of work, the author used publications by such researchers as C. Connors, J. S. Piro, D. Lynch, P. Yenawine, M. C. Opdenakker, J. Van Damme, M. Treve, G. G. Bilgin, C. M. Clark, R. J. Yinger, M. L. Torrijo, A. P. Rico, R. Sani, K. L. Milheim, J. C. Willers, Y. H. Shih, Y. Hod, K. Bielaczyc, D. Ben-Zvi, Chin Ying Liew, G. P. Ryabov, N. A. Mashkovsky, O. N. Smirnov, M. V. Sedelnikova, etc. Their works were published in such journals as *Asian Journal of University Education*; *International Journal of Changes in Education*; *The British Journal of Social Work*; *Theory into Practice*; *Teaching and Teacher Education*; *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*; *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*; *Journal of Learning, Teaching, and Educational Research*; *Curriculum Inquiry*; *History of Education & Children's Literature*; *Journal of Education and Learning*; *Pedagogical Art*; *Pedagogy. Questions of Theory and Practice*; *Yaroslavl Pedagogical Bulletin*; *Historical and Pedagogical Journal*; *Bulletin of the Mari State University*.

RESULTS

The prominent Russian teacher Nikolai Vladimirovich Chekhov was born on June 15 (27), 1865 in St. Petersburg. His father, Vladimir Nikolaevich, graduated from the St. Petersburg Medical and Surgical Academy and devoted himself to psychiatry. Nikolai received his primary education at home. The mother, Lyudmila Alexandrovna, was the daughter of an official of the Ministry of Public Education, a pupil of a boarding school for women. Nikolai had a brother, Vladimir, and sisters Lyudmila and Olga. The mother was engaged in the initial education of children, and the preparation for the gymnasium was done by a home teacher, Vera Vasilyevna Grushko. Instilling love and the habit of reading fiction in children was of great importance in educational work in the family. In 1878, Nikolai immediately entered the 2nd grade of the 6th St. Petersburg Gymnasium, from which he graduated in 1884. A prosperous home environment contributed to the formation of the young man's interest in the humanities, and the formation of his social views was significantly influenced by his cousin, Mikhail Stepanovich Alexandrov (1863-1933), who entered the history of the Bolshevik movement under the pseudonym Olminsky.

In 1884, Chekhov entered the Historical and Philological faculty of the Moscow University. Nikolai's favorite professor was Orest (Oscar) Fedorovich Miller (1833-1889), the head of the student scientific and literary society founded by him in 1882. Chekhov became a member of the society in the 3rd year. In 1886, Alexander Ilyich Ulyanov (1866-1887), a natural science student, was unanimously elected chief secretary of the society. Probably, communication with M. S. Alexandrov and membership in the "Society ..." had a certain political influence on the young Chekhov. Together with other students, he printed and distributed student proclamations, i.e. he was at least in opposition to authorities. However, he didn't belong to any party, although his views were aligned with the Narodniks. He was attracted by the idea of "going to the people"; he was close to the idea of need to "repay the debt to people" through the elimination of illiteracy, the dissemination of knowledge and the organization of reading rooms. Chekhov considered himself one of bourgeois liberals, "culturalists" who were proud that they sacrificed their careers and well-being for the sake of educating people mass. Therefore, he actively participated in the work of the literacy committee at Free Economic Society.

Chekhov's interest in public education developed during his student years. Chekhov worked on a voluntary basis at a school in the village of Volkovo near St. Petersburg, at a Sunday school for workers on the Shlisselburgsky tract behind the Nevsky Outpost, at the very school where N. K. Krupskaya taught in 1891-1896, and here, in February 1894, she first met V. I. Ulyanov (Lenin).

N. V. Chekhov graduated from the university in three years, in 1887, and in two departments at once, – Slavic and historical, receiving a candidate's degree. Having refused the position of head of the Department of Finance, which was advantageous in terms of his official career, he left the capital, and in 1890, together with his wife Maria Alexandrovna, he went for Bogoroditsk, Tula province. Having quickly settled into a new position as head of the economic part of zemstvo schools of the district, the young teacher soon became a close friend in local schools. This modest position seemed to him the most interesting thing. He actually ran schools and did a lot of work with the teaching staff. From week to week, in a peasant cart, on a sleigh, and in the mud on horseback, he traveled through villages of the Tula province. Teachers of the zemstvo schools were mostly peasants who graduated from elementary school, and learned something on their own, and then passed the exam for the title of teacher. In peasant literacy schools, literate teenagers were often teachers. This situation persisted for the first time after the Great October Socialist Revolution, until in 1918 the Soviet government abolished gymnasiums themselves, and unified labor schools were established instead [19, p. 190].

All these teachers remained peasants and "changed the plow to a pointer" with the onset of winter, after the end of agricultural work. Therefore, for them, the advice of a man who graduated from the capital's university was equivalent to a "ray of light in the dark realm" of his own illiteracy, although Chekhov himself didn't have any significant pedagogical experience at that time.

In those years, there was a struggle between the old, letter-based method of literacy teaching, an example of which is given in the passage quoted above, and the sound, analytical and synthetic one. Of course, there were more supporters of the progressive, sound method in the zemstvo schools. In parochial and "house" literacy schools, where teachers were poorly trained people, the "more familiar" letter-compounding method prevailed. But there were many teachers in the Russian province, including those who worked in rural schools, who not only actively applied a more modern method in their work, but even shared their experience at teacher training courses held in provincial and county towns. An example is the activity of an advanced teacher from the Vyatka province, Nikolai Ivanovich Myshkin [20].

N. V. Chekhov put a lot of effort into the introduction of the sound method through methodical training of teachers. To do this, he gave demonstration lessons and conducted their discussion. He sought regular supply of schools through zemstvos with methodological and visual aids, educational literature. Inspector Chekhov had to do a lot of work among peasants, agitating them for opening of schools in villages. Zemstvo's allocations were insufficient, and it was impossible to do without help of rural societies. As a result, over 8 years of Chekhov's work in Bogoroditsky district, the number of primary zemstvo schools increased from 35 to 90. And this is despite the fact that the government pursued a policy of strangling them and planting parish schools. The budget of zemstvo for needs of schools in the county has risen from 7,500 rubles to 40 thousand rubles over years [21, p. 283].

With great enthusiasm, he worked in the commission of folk readings, participated in the creation of the society for the promotion of physical development of children and in the scientific society of Yekaterinoslav, led courses for railway workers, lectured on the history of Russian literature at the local people's University.

The school he was in charge of was distinguished by the progressive nature of teaching. Educational work was well established here, the connection of education with physical labor took place. It was sufficiently provided with the necessary equipment. The school was opened in 1889 with 128 students. The experience of organizing a labor school was conceived and implemented by the head of railway workshops, engineer Peter Ivanovich Khristianovich and an employee of the board Pavel Ivanovich Boulanger, a friend and follower of Leo Tolstoy.

So Chekhov didn't start here from scratch [22, p. 14]. In 1897, when he accepted the school, the number of students was 444, there were 12 classes, 15 teachers. Five years later, when he left the school, the number of students was 1,110, the number of classes was 40, and teachers were 50 [19, p. 192]. Country walks, a student choir, traveling during summer holidays, Sunday readings with a "magic lantern", a Christmas tree, a spring celebration and other events held at the school made children's lives rich and interesting. Chekhov worked with great enthusiasm. "His lessons were attended by teachers of many schools as exemplary. His school became a hotbed of pedagogical knowledge and advanced teaching methods," eyewitnesses recalled [23, p. 48]. In 1900, works of students of the school were exhibited at the World Exhibition in Paris.

Gradually, Chekhov joined the professional teaching movement, began to take an active part in teachers' societies, various educational organizations, literacy committees, local and All-Russian teachers' congresses. His name became dear and close to the advanced progressive-minded teaching [24, p. 39]. Soon Chekhov became a member and then chairman of the teachers' mutual aid society in Tver. He conceived the idea of implementing resolutions of the congress, which concerned the improvement of the legal, material and social status of rural teachers. This bold decision coincided with the government audit of the Tver province. The government led an attack on zemstvo institutions, and the Tver Zemstvo was chosen as the first victim. The entire liberal-minded composition of the zemstvo council wasn't only not approved, but even expelled from the province, "scattered" throughout Russia.

Chekhov ended up in Moscow and joined the large bookselling firm of Ivan Dmitrievich Sytin (1851-1934) as an assistant editor of books for people and children's reading. He wrote a series of short stories for journal "Friend of Children" about foreign writers, a number of popular science articles. During these years, he launched a stormy social activity, became one of the founders of the All-Russian Teachers' Union (1905). He was a participant and organizer of all teachers' congresses of those years. Chekhov actively manifested himself at the 2nd Congress of teachers on technical and vocational education (1895-1896, Moscow), which became, in fact, the first socially significant performance of Russian teachers in pre-October period. In April 1908, he made a report on the situation of the All-Russian Union of Teachers at a conference of representatives of teachers' unions, including national ones. In his speech, he noted that with all diversity of nationalities inhabiting Russia and difference in local conditions, one teaching organization can't serve needs of the entire teaching staff of Russia. Therefore, a number of alliances are needed. In this regard, he welcomed the establishment of national teachers' unions.

In 1906-1909, Chekhov worked at the St. Petersburg Zemstvo Teachers' Seminary. He taught literature and methods of Russian. In his work with future teachers, he paid great attention to extracurricular activities: literary and artistic evenings, city tours, visits to theaters, exhibitions. "He brought a ray of light into zemstvo teaching environment," recalled one of his former students. "Chekhov turned out to be an indispensable person, – director A. K. Yanson said about him. – Everyone was amazed by his extraordinary good-nature and calmness. Disciples fought with everyone, but not with him: he disarmed them. I found such a comrade and friend in him that I can't even imagine how I would have done my job without him. It was my conscience and my faith. How we, teachers and students, grieved when he left us" [25, p. 194].

In 1909, Chekhov joined the Moscow City Council, where he continued his educational activities. However, the mayor N. K. Guchkov soon dismissed Chekhov, telling him: "I know that you are doing a lot, but you aren't doing what we need at all; your activities are harmful to us" [26, p. 79]. Chekhov's dismissal caused a storm of protest from progressive public. 423 teachers in Moscow signed a commemorative address, which contained the following words: "You, Nikolai Vladimirovich, are one of those who carry cheerfulness to everywhere and strive to awaken it in others ..." The letter expressed confidence that the time isn't far off when to realize ideals for which Chekhov is fighting a different, more favorable soil will be created [27, p. 160]. After his dismissal from the board, Chekhov joined the Moscow women's pedagogical courses of D. I. Tikhomirov as a teacher, and soon he was elected chairman of pedagogical section of courses. For future teachers, he taught a course on methods of teaching the Russian language, a course on

school organization, and reviewed children's and folk literature. In the pre-October years, Chekhov wrote a number of books that brought him fame as a historian of pedagogy. His monograph "Public Education in Russia since the 60s of the nineteenth century" (1912) stands out in particular, which has become a reference book for every serious researcher of the history of Russian pedagogy. In total, he published over seven hundred works.

In 1916, together with his family, – Chekhov had seven children, – he moved to Voronezh, where he organized two-year pedagogical zemstvo courses for teachers, which he supervised until 1919 (Later, a pedagogical institute was opened on their basis). In September 1920, Chekhov was invited to the People's Commissariat of Education (further – PCE) of the RSFSR to work as a member of the commission of the unified school department. Two years later, he was appointed head of the department of experimental and demonstration institutions of the PCE. In 1927-1930 he was in charge of the school department.

In the early 1920s, such innovative forms of school business organization as experimental educational institutions (commune schools, school towns) began to appear in the country. Their appearance was caused by a desire of advanced teachers to find new ways of educating and educating younger generation. One of the country's famous commune schools was headed by Vyatka teacher Anatoly Ivanovich Kondakov (1892-1979), who created it in the village of Znamenka, Yaransk district, Vyatka province. He told about it in the book "School commune" (Moscow, 1961). Chekhov actively supported the creation of a network of experimental institutions. The idea, in principle, was this: to teach the rest on the experience of the best, thereby spreading advanced pedagogical experience [28, p. 72]. He organized five conferences on this issue. But progressive democratic experiments in the field of education didn't last long [29, p. 149]. The administrative and bureaucratic system didn't need pedagogical associations of a communal type, and soon all these educational institutions were liquidated. At first, leading figures of the PCE, such as N. K. Krupskaya and S. T. Shatsky, were active conductors of this idea to the teaching masses, but, after only a few years, they were forced to abandon their innovative views [30, p. 82]. So, in 1925, the Znamenka school campus, among other institutions of this type, ended its existence [31, p. 65]. It was transformed into an agricultural college, which, by the way, still exists today. The liquidation even caused Krupskaya regret. After learning about it, she said: "How? Why? By whose order?" [32, p. 34]. Alas, neither Krupskaya nor Chekhov could really help in any way.

Subsequently, Chekhov became the scientific supervisor of graduate student A. I. Kondakov, who in his memoirs warmly recalled him, who retained "until the end of his life features of a simple folk teacher, an open cheerful person with a broad Russian soul, a wise and benevolent adviser" [33, p. 15]. Anatoly Ivanovich's son Victor worked as an associate professor of the department of Physics at the Kirov and then at the Kuibyshev (Samara) pedagogical institutes. The author of this article communicated with him a lot, and the information obtained in communication with Victor was partially used in writing this article.

In 1919-1920, Chekhov was in charge of school departments in several districts of Moscow. In the 1920s, in addition to his main job, he joined work on elimination of illiteracy in the Red Army, and he trained teachers from war invalids. He was a member of the Central Committee of the Society "Down with Illiteracy" (1920-1929), took an active part in the issue of the journal "For Literacy". Chekhov worked in the PCE in 1923-1930 in the department of universal education and in the commission for education of nationalities. He served as a professor at the Pedagogical Faculty of the 2nd Moscow State University, in 1925-1930. He worked as a professor of higher pedagogical courses, at the Institute for Advanced Training of Teachers, at the Library Institute (1942-1945), as well as in research institutions (1919-1947), in particular, at the Scientific Institute of Pedagogy (1926-1930), at the State Institute of Schools (1938-1944), at the APS of the RSFSR as director of the archive (1944-1945), at the Research Institute of Children's Reading and at the Children's Book Museum (1933-1937). In 1945-1947 he was a researcher at the Institute of Theory and History of Pedagogy and the Institute of Teaching Methods of the APS. In 1940, he was awarded the degree of doctor of pedagogical sciences without defending his dissertation. Chekhov was one of the first twelve full members of the APS (1943).

He was the author of textbooks "Russian for Tatars (M., 1929), "Teaching Russian to non-Russian adults" (M., 1929), "Teaching Russian colloquial speech to non-Russian adults" (M., 1929), "Russian language in schools of national minorities" (M., 1928), In total, he was author of over 800 works on pedagogy, history of public education, school studies, organization of public education, children's literature and children's reading, methods of teaching Russian, textbooks and teaching aids.

DISCUSSION

The pedagogical worldview of Chekhov was formed under the influence of views of revolutionary democrats. In accordance with general democratic views, he stood for a broad general education, against the narrowness and utilitarianism of curricula. He always emphasized the importance of educative learning. He considered his native language to be the main academic subject of the folk school. According to the teacher, school should educate children in the spirit of its people, acquaint them with the character of people and its ideals. He was particularly fond of studying children's literature and children's reading. His knowledge of child psychology and literature allowed him to develop in detail a methodology for teaching reading to children of different ages in classroom and at home. On this issue, he published books "Children's Literature", "Companion of self-education", "Children's book and children's reading", "The latest trends in teaching Russian in elementary school".

Chekhov made a significant contribution to the theory of the issue of visual learning. In the book "The visibility of learning and visual aids in elementary school" (Moscow, 1904, 1911), he described in detail the types of visibility and the methodology of their use. He attached particular importance to reading natural science texts in textbooks, since there were no subjects such as history, zoology, botany, geography in elementary school. The teacher paid great attention to arithmetic, the teaching of which, he believed, should be conducted as close as possible to the actual counting of subjects included in the circle of living conditions of students and their families. Singing, drawing, modeling and expressive reading contribute to the moral and aesthetic education of students [34].

Chekhov's views weren't always supported by colleagues. So, now it seems incredible, but he had to defend the validity of the very concept of "children's literature". Subversives, such as the naturalist, historian and writer Yevgeny Alexandrovich Yelachich (1880-1944), denied children's books the right to exist, stating, in particular, that fairy tales should be banned because they give a "distorted picture of the world." And this was said by a man who was himself a children's writer! Chekhov opposed gray books, "Pinkertonism"; books where the characters were stilted, and their actions were formulaic. He named Lydia Alekseevna Charskaya (1875-1937) as an example of the author of such books.

Chekhov was the initiator of the creation of the Research Institute of Children's Literature and an active employee of the children's book museum. At his suggestion, a commission was formed to collect materials related to the history of children's literature. At the beginning of his pedagogical activity, Chekhov called for the formation of a new type of teacher, a peasant teacher, who, in his opinion, had to merge with villagers; live with them the same life and the same worries, only occasionally breaking away from his peasant affairs in order to work as a teacher.

At that time, he was closely associated with the work of the Moscow and St. Petersburg Literacy Committees, at whose meetings in the 1890s the issues of primary public education were acutely raised. And so, on December 13, 1893, he made a presentation at a meeting of the Moscow Committee on "Literacy schools and peasant teachers." Peasant literacy schools, he said, still played a positive role, and they needed to be introduced into the organization of universal education.

A prominent teacher D. I. Tikhomirov objected to him, saying that an idea of the school being close to the people captivated everyone. But the school that Chekhov defended had long been known: it taught only mechanical reading, bad writing and reading in Church Slavonic, without translation. The teacher in it was an "artisanal trowel" who looked at school only as an income and could give children nothing but mechanical training. Objecting to his opponents, Chekhov continued to defend literacy schools as necessary for the fastest implementation of universal primary education. Subsequently, he realized the fallacy of his view of literacy schools and peasant teachers without special training. Only a zemstvo school with a professional teacher, with stable textbooks and

programs, regularly funded, could have a perspective. Chekhov outlined his later views, including on this survey, in the collection "The Needs of the Village", which gave a critical assessment of the state of public education in Russia [26, p. 16].

CONCLUSIONS

Honored Scientist of the RSFSR (1944), Professor, doctor of pedagogical sciences, Chekhov enjoyed great respect and love of teachers. His eightieth birthday, which coincided with the end of the Great Patriotic War, was widely celebrated by the pedagogical community. On this occasion, a special solemn meeting of the APS was held. In his speech at this meeting, People's Commissar of Education V. P. Potemkin noted: «In your person we all appreciate and honor the living and vivid embodiment of the rich experience of several generations of national teachers. In the vast family of public education figures of our country, you have an undeniable place as an honorary veteran, the oldest of the old teachers, to whose authoritative voice our pedagogical community always listens sensitively... A distinctive feature that always characterizes your creative and social work is the unusual ability to combine practice with theory and theory with practice" [35].

Pedagogical publications gave reports from this meeting. Chekhov was awarded the Order of Lenin. Even earlier, he was awarded the honorary title "Honored Scientist of the RSFSR", was awarded the Order of the Red Banner of Labor. But the days of Chekhov were already numbered. On November 8, 1947, he died. The pedagogical legacy of the remarkable Russian teacher, educator and organizer of public education attracts the attention of modern researchers for its depth, vastness, as well as the fact that in his publications the author touched on a wide variety of topics. Therefore, it requires further study, especially in the field of children's literature problems. The author of this article included N. V. Chekhov among the 100 great teachers in his book of the same title [36, p. 326].

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Вклад автора

Помелов В. Б.: концептуализация, методология,
создание рукописи и её редактирование

Author contribution

Vladimir B. Pomelov: Conceptualization, Methodology,
Writing - Review & Editing

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Автор заявляет об отсутствии конфликта интересов

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The author declared no conflicts of interest